

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING COMPETITIVE STRATEGIES IN AZERBAIJAN'S LOGISTICS SERVICES

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Abstract

The article analyzes the current state of logistics services in Azerbaijan and explores ways to improve competitive strategies for the development of this sector. It highlights the country's favorable geographical location and its strategic role in the East-West and North-South transport corridors. The importance of logistics in economic growth, strengthening the service sector, and expanding international trade relations is emphasized. The study shows that infrastructure projects implemented in recent years have enabled Azerbaijan to become a regional logistics hub. The article also highlights the impact of the Russia-Ukraine war on global trade routes and emphasizes the importance of the Middle Corridor route, within which Azerbaijan is seen as gaining new opportunities. Overall, the article presents both theoretically and practically that the modernization of logistics infrastructure, the involvement of the private sector, digitalization, and international cooperation should be prioritized as key areas for improving competitive strategies.

Keywords: competitive strategies, transport corridors, logistics infrastructure, service sector, logistics services, competitiveness-oriented strategic development, regional logistics hubs.

Introduction

Since the 1990s, the Republic of Azerbaijan has declared its political sovereignty, achieved economic independence, and ensured the comprehensive development of various infrastructure sectors [7, p.31]. This infrastructure development and economic independence have created a favorable foundation for the rapid and high-quality development of the service sector in the country.

However, the results of macroeconomic research indicate that, in terms of growth rates, Azerbaijan still lags behind economically developed countries in certain essential services (such as healthcare, culture, education, transportation, etc.). Furthermore, in Western Europe, North America, as well as countries like Japan, Malaysia, Singapore, and others, the share of service employment related to knowledge-intensive activities is higher than in Azerbaijan [5, p.4]. In this regard, the analysis of the development level of the service sector is both one of the key indicators of economic growth and an important factor for the deepening of social welfare.

The service sector, as one of the material production sectors, is a crucial component of society's productive activity. In recent years, the development of the service sector reflects the distinctive characteristics of the Azerbaijani economy. This type of economic dynamics arises, on the one hand, from changes in the purposeful structure of business, and on the other hand, from the increase in the real income of the population [5, p.4]. All these processes further highlight the growing significance of the service sector, both locally and globally, making it essential to analyze the development trends of this sector in a broader context.

The 21st century, characterized by the intensification of globalization and integration processes, is also remembered as an information age, marked by the rapid development of the service sector

in the economic field. Observations show that, in recent decades, the share and role of the service sector in the economy have been increasing, which can be attributed to two main reasons. First, the increase in people's income allows for a higher expenditure not only on physical goods but also on services. The second reason is the development of ICT, which has expanded the possibilities of the service sector and increased its economic value. Experience has shown that, precisely due to these reasons, starting from the second half of the 20th century, in developed countries, the service sector began to outpace the production sector. As a result, today, the service sector holds a larger share in GDP formation and employment provision in most countries around the world. The growing market share of the service sector has, in fact, ensured the diversification of the economy and specialization across sectors. Although there are rich potential opportunities for the development of most service sectors in the Republic of Azerbaijan, the share of this sector in GDP fluctuates between 26-33%. This indicates that the existing potential in service sectors is not fully and effectively utilized in our country. [1, p.6-20]

The results obtained show that the role of the service sector in economic development is continuously increasing in a globalized world, and the demand for this sector necessitates the implementation of new approaches. In this context, the logistics system, being one of the most important areas of the service sector, holds significant importance. The proper organization and management of logistics services have a substantial impact on both the efficiency of the national economy and international competitiveness.

Logistics is a theoretical and practical field of activity related to the planning, organization, functional management, and control of the movement of material, labor, financial, and informational flows within a

market economy system. Logistics attempts to regulate all processes associated with the production of goods and the provision of services, from suppliers to final consumers. Based on this logic, it can be concluded that logistics is a necessity for the modern stage of economic development. [4, p.36]

Logistics services play a crucial role in the efficient and sustainable operation of the national economy. These services ensure the correct and coordinated delivery of goods and services from production to the consumer, thus fulfilling the function of maintaining the continuous operation of the economic system. The improvement of logistics services enhances the efficiency of economic activities.

The development of foreign trade is also one of the important directions in which logistics impacts the economy. The efficient implementation of import and export operations and the development of transportation and logistics infrastructures strengthen the country's position in international trade. In this regard, Azerbaijan holds strategic importance as a transit country along the Middle Corridor and North-South transport routes.

The logistics value chain creates economic value at each stage. The processes of warehousing, transportation, and information management services along the path from production to final consumption directly affect the quality and market price of the product. This, in turn, is considered one of the key factors influencing the overall competitiveness of enterprises. At the same time, the logistics sector creates significant employment opportunities, contributing to the improvement of socio-economic welfare. Many companies operate in this sector, dealing with transit services and warehousing. Thus, logistics is considered a significant sector both economically and socially.

The efficient organization of logistics strategies is a crucial issue for gaining a competitive advantage in both domestic and international markets. In this regard, improvements in this area can have a positive impact on the development of the service sector. One of the key issues in our country in this field may be increasing the role of logistics in regional economic development. In this context, the establishment of logistics centers, warehouses, and transport corridors in the regions may be vital for enhancing the economic potential of these areas. This can also lead to the creation of new investments and job opportunities.

As a result, logistics services serve as one of the main sectors within the service industry in the national

economy. Their development creates a foundation for the formation of a long-term competitive environment within the service sector. Thus, on one hand, the increasing intensity of interest and demand for the application of logistical approaches is determined by the demands and outcomes of market relations. On the other hand, the acceleration of logistics management and its wide application in economic life have a significant impact on the improvement of the market relations system and the country's economic policy course. [3, p.106]

Contents of the study

Azerbaijan's advantageous geographical location allows for the continuous enhancement of its trade potential. The constant improvement of Azerbaijan's logistics sector has led to an increased role in both regional and international markets. In general, due to the favorable geographical position of our country in both the East-West and North-South corridors, Azerbaijan has the opportunity to obtain a significant share from both transit trade and import-export operations. Several major infrastructure projects, such as ports and railways, have been implemented in the country. Considering the above, the improvement of logistics infrastructures in Azerbaijan, increasing the level of private sector participation, boosting revenues from transit trade, and increasing the service sector's share in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) could lead to the growth of trade volume.

The development of logistics in Azerbaijan is not only related to utilizing the positive aspects of the country's geographical location but also to the implementation of modern infrastructure projects. In this regard, the operations of the Absheron logistics center ensure the further strengthening of the country's position in international trade and transit operations.

The Absheron logistics center, which is a private logistics hub in Azerbaijan, complies with international standards and certifications and is located at the heart of the Great Silk Road. Since its inception on August 13, 2018, in the Lokbatan settlement, the center allows for direct access from the terminal to the main road transport routes, enabling faster delivery to the target. Equipped with strong infrastructure facilities, high service quality, modern technologies, and rich operational capabilities, the center conducts transit customs operations through the customs authorities located on-site. The logistics center provides services through a "single window" system, which saves time and reduces costs. [8]

Figure 1. Services of the Absheron logistics center. Note: The figure is prepared by the author.

In addition, The Fruit Limited Liability Company (“Meyvəli”) was established on May 16, 2008, by a group of entrepreneurs. The main activity of the “Meyvəli” logistics center is the wholesale and retail distribution of fruits and vegetables. The primary goal of the logistics center's establishment is to meet the demands of the Azerbaijani population and to facilitate the timely, safe, and efficient delivery of agricultural products produced by local farmers to the local market. To achieve this, the “Meyvəli” logistics center is strategically located on the outskirts of the city, at the entrance to Baku. Its favorable location has made it easier to transport agricultural products from every region of the country to the capital. In addition, the “Meyvəli” logistics center offers refrigerated warehouses for public use. Products stored in these warehouses do not lose their quality, and farmers have the opportunity to store their products here. The establishment of the “Meyvəli” logistics center has had a positive impact not only on the region but also within the Commonwealth of Independent States area, creating a fruit and vegetable base that is unparalleled. It has contributed to the country's development, improved the welfare of the population, and created new job opportunities. [9]

The logistics sector in Azerbaijan is still in its early stages, but it holds significant potential. For many, a logistics center is nothing more than a warehouse whose sole purpose is to store goods. For these reasons, the current logistics market is small. However, recent global political tensions have created several

perspectives for the development of logistics in our country.

Thus, the rapidly changing geopolitical situation against the backdrop of the Russia-Ukraine war has not only increased global security risks but has also directly impacted global trade. Since the outbreak of the war in 2022, the importance of traditional trade routes connecting Europe and Asia has diminished, while the significance of new alternative trade corridors has risen. In this context, one of the main alternative trade corridors connecting Western countries to the Asia region is the Middle Corridor route. Known primarily as the Middle Corridor and of special strategic importance, one of the key participants in this corridor is Azerbaijan.

Azerbaijan's key strategic advantage in this project is its ability to connect the Central Asia region to Turkey and subsequently to Europe via the Caspian Sea basin. Undoubtedly, Azerbaijan, which has turned its geographic advantage into one of the main mechanisms of its foreign policy influence, aims to become one of the world's leading logistics centers. In pursuit of this goal, Azerbaijan has implemented a number of strategically significant transportation and logistics projects in recent years. For instance, in 2024, Azerbaijan successfully completed the modernization of the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway line, and based on the president's instructions, the master plan for the second phase of the expansion of the Baku International Sea Trade Port is currently being prepared.

Figure 2. The Middle Corridor route connecting Western countries with the Asian region. Note: The figure was compiled by the author.

The Middle Corridor - Trans-Caspian International Transport Route, which holds significant strategic importance on the Eurasian continent, is an international trade and transport route stretching from China to Europe through Central Asia, the Caspian Sea, the South Caucasus, and Turkey. The countries marked in dark blue on the map - Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Turkey are considered the main transit and connecting countries along this route.

Azerbaijan plays a central role in the Middle Corridor. The country's access to the Caspian Sea and the Baku International Sea Trade Port serves as a key bridge along this route. At the same time, through the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway, Azerbaijan acts as one of the main transit corridors for the delivery of cargo to

Europe. The logistics and infrastructure projects implemented by Azerbaijan - particularly the Alat Free Economic Zone - contribute to strengthening this strategic position. The Middle Corridor is considered a strategic transportation project, especially in terms of providing a fast and secure connection between Europe and Asia. Additionally, this corridor constitutes an important component of China's "Belt and Road" initiative.

Taking all these factors into account, Azerbaijan has recently been engaging in collaborations with Turkey, Georgia, China, and the Central Asian republics to develop new projects aimed at advancing the logistics sector.

During the visits of the delegation of Azerbaijan Railways (ADY) to China and Central Asian countries,

discussions were held with counterparts on strengthening cooperation in the railway sector, increasing freight turnover, expanding the volume of multimodal cargo transportation along the Central Asia-Europe-Central Asia and China-Europe-China corridors, attracting new cargo flows to the Middle Corridor, and promoting the potential of this corridor in European markets. The discussions and resulting agreements constitute an essential component of the structural and financial reforms implemented in Azerbaijan's transport sector in recent years.

It should be noted that significant structural and financial changes have taken place in Azerbaijan's transport sector over the past 20 years. The purposeful orientation of state policy towards this field, particularly the attraction of large-scale investments for the reconstruction of the liberated territories, has elevated the transport infrastructure to a qualitatively new stage. All the work carried out is clearly reflected in the statistical indicators. From this perspective, the analysis of key macroeconomic indicators related to transportation is considered effective.

Graph 1. Investments directed to fixed capital in the transport sector in Azerbaijan, million manats. The source: Compiled based on the data from the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan (SSCRA). [6, p.9]

Graph 1 clearly shows that in Azerbaijan, investments directed to fixed capital in the transport sector were significantly low in the year 2000 - amounting to only 44 million manats. By 2005, this figure had risen to 516 million, marking the beginning of a phase of substantial growth. In 2010, investments increased even more sharply, reaching 2,435 million manats. During this period, large-scale infrastructure projects were implemented in the country, including the reconstruction of major roads and integration into international transport corridors.

A certain decline was observed in 2015 and 2020, amounting to 2,195 million manats and 2,092 million

manats, respectively. This is considered to be associated with global economic instability, fluctuations in oil prices, and the postponement of some domestic projects. However, a significant increase has been recorded since 2021. Investments, which stood at 2,857 million manats in 2021, rose to 4,613 million manats in 2022. In 2023, the highest figure-5,417 million manats- was registered. This growth is mainly attributed to the reconstruction of transport infrastructure, including the construction of railways and highways, in the liberated territories. Now, let us examine the net profit indicators in the transport sector in Azerbaijan. (Graph 2.).

Graph 2. Net profit from transportation in Azerbaijan (at current prices), in million manat. The source: Compiled based on the data from the SSCRA. [6, p.9]

In Azerbaijan, the net profit in the transportation sector was at a very low level between 2000 and 2005, showing a slight increase from 229 million manat to 275 million manat. The real breakthrough occurred in 2010, when the sector achieved significant progress in terms of profitability, reaching 1,576 million manat. In 2015, the net profit amounted to 1,860 million manat, and in 2020, it rose to 2,534 million manat. During this period, the sector demonstrated stable development. In 2021 and 2022, net profit reached its highest levels, with figures of 4,054 million manat and 5,136 million manat, respectively. However, in 2023, a decline in this indicator was observed, with net profit falling to 4,657 million manat. This decline may be attributed to several factors: the time required for investments to convert into revenue, some projects not yet generating income, or rising costs (such as the increase in construction material prices, labor costs, etc.).

When examining the relationships between the two graphs, it is clear that there is a direct correlation between the increase in investments directed towards

fixed capital and the growth of net profit. However, this correlation sometimes manifests with a delayed effect. For instance, in 2022, both investments and profits reached their peak, but in 2023, while investments increased, profits declined. This indicates that investments do not immediately generate returns-profitability may materialize several years later.

Overall, the graphs demonstrate that investments in the transportation sector gradually yield economic results, and this sector is becoming one of the sustainable pillars of the national economy.

During the indicators, reflecting only the current prices leads to an analysis without considering the impact of inflation. Therefore, when making comparisons between years, it becomes difficult to determine how much of the increase is real, as the purchasing power of the manat may change. Considering this, it is deemed efficient to present an additional graph based on inflation-adjusted indicators at real prices and conduct an evaluation.

Graph 3. Annual inflation in Azerbaijan, in percent (%). The source: Compiled based on the data from the SSCRA. [11]

To understand how real the increases in the indicators are, it is necessary to consider the impact of inflation. Therefore, the analysis related to inflation can be carried out as follows (Graph 1):

- 2000 - The inflation rate was 1.81%. This is relatively low, and the comparison of the figures with real values is not very significant.
- 2005 - The inflation rate was 9.68%, which is quite high. This could result in future increases being real lower. The reported increase of 516 million manat, when adjusted for inflation, may not be as high as it initially seems.
- 2010 - The inflation rate was 5.73%. The increase of 2,435 million manat, while high in real terms, has been diminished in value when adjusted for inflation.
- 2015 - The inflation rate was 4.03%, and a significant increase occurred during this period. The investment of 2,195 million manat, when valued at real prices, remains significant.
- 2020 - The inflation rate was 2.76%. The investment of 2,092 million manat during this period is considered relatively high when compared to inflation.
- 2021 - The inflation rate was 6.65%, yet the investment was 2,857 million manat. Despite high inflation, this indicates a strong increase in investment.

- 2022 - The inflation rate reached 13.85%, which is very high. The increase in investment, totaling 4,613 million manat, may not appear as significant when compared to real values due to the impact of inflation.

- 2023 - The inflation rate was 8.79%. The decline in net profit this year could be due to the effects of inflation and the rise in costs. Despite an investment of 5,417 million manat, the inflation factor diminishes this increase.

The inflation analysis indicates that, in some years, investment growth may decline due to the impact of inflation. However, with the future development of the transport sector and the continuation of strategic infrastructure projects, Azerbaijan can continue to generate revenue in this field. The implementation of innovative logistics projects is considered essential to ensure high returns on new investments.

Proposals

After all the analyses, it can be stated that the logistics sector in the service industry has become one of the priority areas in Azerbaijan in recent years. This growing interest in the sector can be observed through the investments directed towards it. In this regard, considering this interest, the primary goal should be to achieve high profits with minimal costs. Therefore, the implementation of innovative projects in the logistics

service sector in the country could lead to an increase in the sector's share in the GDP and the creation of new job opportunities. In this context, the implementation of a number of projects is considered to be efficient.

1. Creation of Regional Logistics Hubs in the liberated territories. It may be possible to transform the liberated territories into logistics hubs of the South Caucasus by establishing strategic transportation and trade centers in these areas. In particular, the creation of logistics hubs in the Zangilan region, considering the location of the Zangezur Corridor and its proximity to Iran and Nakhchivan, could be efficient. Additionally, implementing such a project in Fuzuli, given the presence of the international airport and the Fuzuli-Aghband railway, could yield high efficiency. These centers can facilitate the development of the service sector by creating the infrastructures listed below: [10]

- Dual-purpose warehouses
- Passenger and cargo terminal
- Customs-broker service offices
- Logistics incubators for small and medium-sized entrepreneurs
- Packaging and labeling centers for entrepreneurs

The benefits that can be obtained from centers:

- The interregional movement of goods could be accelerated, with products coming from Kalbajar, Tovuz, and other areas, and being loaded in Zangilan.
- Foreign companies, particularly from Turkey and Central Asian countries, could utilize these hubs.
- The country's and region's currency flow could increase, which would consequently boost state revenues.
- Jobs would be created, and the return of internally displaced persons to the areas could be expedited.

2. The establishment of logistics service centers.

These centers are multifunctional office and facility complexes that offer all services in one place for companies and entrepreneurs engaged in logistics. In these centers, transportation, storage, packaging, documentation, customs, export, and import services are provided in one location, as part of a single "system." This means that entrepreneurs or carriers can address all their logistics needs in one place without having to go to separate locations. Here, services such as customs services, documentation, registration and training of carriers, warehouse rental services, and cargo insurance are available. [12]

The establishment of logistics service centers in the outskirts of Baku, particularly in areas such as Hövsan and Zabrat, as well as at the Ganja-Samukh junction, and in the regions of Zangilan and Fuzuli, could be highly beneficial for regional trade. These centers could provide several positive advantages for the service sector, especially in the logistics field, including the following:

- Small entrepreneurs have the opportunity to introduce their products to the international market.
- Access to services is simplified, and costs are reduced.
- The performance indicators of the logistics sector in the service industry are improving.

Result

The role of logistics services in Azerbaijan's economic development is increasingly growing. Strengthening the competitiveness of this sector is one of the key steps toward transforming the country into a regional and international transport and transit hub. The analyses conducted in the article demonstrate that, in the context of the development of the non-oil sector, improving the quality of logistics services, the implementation of digital technologies, the proper formulation of competitive strategies, and the integration of local companies into international practices are essential conditions.

Research shows that in the modern era, logistics is not only the transportation of goods and services but also one of the key instruments in shaping the economic security and competitiveness of countries. Based on the analysis conducted in this article, it can be concluded that the correct and comprehensive application of competitive strategies in the development of logistics services in Azerbaijan is of paramount importance. Although there have been certain achievements in this field, more efficient and innovative strategies are needed in the face of global and regional challenges.

In a time when digitalization is rapidly advancing, the adaptation of logistics services to this technological transformation, as well as the implementation of digital platforms and smart management systems, emerges as a crucial factor.

Azerbaijan's favorable geographical location, access to international transport corridors, and the ongoing reconstruction process in the region create strategic advantages in this field. As a result, improving the competitive strategies in Azerbaijan's logistics services can not only increase economic efficiency but also strengthen the country's regional leadership and help establish an image of a reliable partner in the global trade system.

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